

Predatory effect of *Alcaeorrhynchus grandis* on grub and pupa of *Coccinella septumpunctata*

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Short Communication Short Communication Received on Feb 13, 2020 Revised on March 17, 2020 Accepted on April 09, 2020 Published on April 21, 2020</p> <p>Article Authors Sundar Pal, Prabhat Tiwari Corresponding Author Email sun.csaent@gmail.com</p>	<p>Lady bird beetle, <i>Coccinella septumpunctata</i> is a predator in the nature on different soft body insect in different crops. This beetle is beneficial for farmers as bio control agents but in nature, its population being affected by <i>Alcaeorrhynchus grandis</i> which acts as a predator on larval and pupal stages. It is a sting bug that sucks the body just of this insect. In <i>Coccinella septumpunctata</i>, 50 per cent population of grub and 100 per cent population of pupa was shown predatory effect were noticed at 15th SW.</p>
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Alcaeorrhynchus grandis has been reported from Brazil, Colombia, Mexico, and the southern United States (Ribeiro *et al.*, 2010). *Alcaeorrhynchus grandis* (Dallas) sometimes called the giant strong-nosed stink bug, is a very large (20 mm) predatory stink bug which occurs in several row crops and preys on other insects, especially lepidopteran larvae. The stages in the life cycle are presented here so that they can be identified in the field. Although little has been written on this species, it has been reported to be an important predator of soybean pests in Florida (Watson, 1916 and Whitcomb, 1973). It has also been reported to be a pest on eggplant (Watson, 1922) but damage to any crops by this species is probably exceptional.

All totaled, 57 species are now known from the state, eight of which represent new state records: Asopinae: *Alcaeorrhynchus grandis* (Dallas), *Tylospilus acutissimus* (Stal), Pentatominae: *Banasa calua* (Say), *Banasa euchlora* Stal, *Cosmopepla intergressa* (Uhler), *Halyomorpha halys* (Stal), Neottiglossa undata (Say), Podopinae: *Amaurochrous breuitylus* Barber and Sailer (Sites *et al.*, 2012). Adults and larvae of *Coccinella septempunctata* L feeds on some aphid species, it has been shown to be an important predator of psyllids (Michaud, 2001).

Materials and Methods

The observation was recorded on brinjal crop was grown on Vegetable Cafeteria of Rani Lakshmi Bai Central Agricultural University, Jhansi, UP, India during rabi season 2018-19. Data was collected on five plants which were randomly selected from field and the counting of the healthy and unhealthy/ killed grubs, pupas and adults was done from hall areal parts of plants.

Results and Discussion

The relative population of lady bird beetle was first time noticed from the brinjal field of 5th

standard week (SW). The grub population of lady bird beetle were recorded as 6.00±1.00, 9.00±1.00, 15.67±1.53, 20.00±8.89, 15.67±5.13, 30.67±7.09, 22.33±8.50, 12.33±1.53, 9.00±1.00, 4.33±0.58 and 1.33±0.58 grubs/plant/week from 5th SW to 15th SW, respectively. Observation was recorded on pupa population of *Coccinella septempunctata* from 5th to 15th SW. The population range was 2.33±0.58-48.67±7.64 pupas/plant/week. The maximum population was recorded from 10th SW. Population was first time recorded as 9.67±2.08 pupas/plant/week which was continue increased to 10th SW but after that it was decrease and last record was minimum population during this study period.

Table 1. Predatory effect of stink bug on grubs and pupa of *Coccinella septempunctata* in brinjal crop during rabi season 2018-19

SW	Population (Mean±SD)							
	<i>Coccinella septempunctata</i>			Stink Bug	Predatory Effect of Stink Bug			
	Grub	Pupa	Adult		Grubs	(%)	Pupa	(%)
5	6.00±1.00	9.67±2.08	4.00±1.00	1.33±0.58	0.67±0.58	11.17	3.33±2.08	34.44
6	9.00±1.00	19.67±5.51	5.67±1.53	1.33±0.58	1.33±0.58	14.78	3.67±2.08	18.66
7	15.67±1.53	36.00±5.00	8.33±1.15	2.00±1.00	1.67±0.58	10.66	8.67±4.51	24.08
8	20.00±8.89	29.33±3.79	15.00±2.65	1.33±0.58	1.33±0.58	6.65	14.00±3.61	47.73
9	15.67±5.13	26.00±1.73	12.67±1.53	2.33±1.53	1.33±0.58	8.49	11.67±2.08	44.88
10	30.67±7.09	48.67±7.64	13.33±2.31	3.33±2.08	3.00±2.65	9.78	24.33±5.13	49.99
11	22.33±8.50	43.67±3.21	12.67±4.04	2.67±0.58	2.67±1.15	11.96	27.67±2.52	63.36
12	12.33±1.53	29.33±6.43	6.67±2.08	1.33±0.58	2.00±1.00	16.22	13.67±1.53	46.61
13	9.00±1.00	15.67±1.53	3.00±1.00	1.33±0.58	1.33±0.58	14.78	8.33±2.08	53.16
14	4.33±0.58	8.33±1.53	2.33±0.58	0.67±0.58	0.67±0.58	15.47	6.00±1.73	72.03
15	1.33±0.58	2.33±0.58	0.67±0.58	0.67±0.58	0.67±0.58	50.38	2.33±0.58	100.00

The grubs and adults of *C. septempunctata* appeared on the crop during mid February and their population increased with the increase in aphid population (Soni *et al.*, 2013). The adult population was maximum (15.00±2.65 adults/plant/week) recorded from 8th SW. The adult population was fluctuating during study period and a range was noticed as 0.67±0.58-15.00±2.65 adults/plant/week. The population was start with 4.00±1.00 adults/plant/week and the end of season was minimum recorded.

The maximum number of ladybeetles (*C. septempunctata*, *C. transversalis* and *M. sexmaculatus*) was obtained as 5.00, 3.00 and 3.50; 7.00, 3.50 and 4.00; 9.00, 4.00 and 3.00 in March 2010 and 5.00, 3.50 and 2.50, 5.00, 4.00 and 3.00, 8.00, 5.00 and 3.50 during March 2011, respectively (Ali and Rana, 2012).

Population of stink bug was first time noticed with 1.33±0.58 adults/plant/week from 5th SW. The peak population was recorded (3.33±2.08 adults/plant/week) when grub and pupa population was on peak during study period. The population range was recorded as 0.67±0.58-3.33±2.08 adults/plant/week during study period. Smith *et al.*, (2009) were recorded the average density (mean +/- SEM) of stink bugs across all soybean samples was 1.84 +/- 0.06 per 25 sweeps. Peak densities of stink bugs in soybean were observed during the full-pod (R7) developmental stage. Malaguido *et al.* (1998) were observe that *Alcaeorrhynchus grandis* (Dallas) (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae: Asopinae) preying on larvae of *Chlosyne lacinia* and sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) at an experimental station in northern Parana State, Brazil in January-February 1998.

Observation on predatory effect of stink bug on grub and pupa of *Coccinella septumpunctata* was maximum 3.00 ± 2.65 grubs/plant/week and 27.67 ± 2.52 pupas/plant/week from 10th and 11th SW. The grub infestation per cent was 11.17, 14.78, 10.66, 6.65, 8.49, 9.78, 11.96, 16.22, 14.78, 15.47 and 50.38 from 5th to 15th SW, respectively. The pupa infestation per cent was 34.44, 18.66, 24.08, 47.73, 44.88, 49.99, 63.36, 46.61, 53.16, 72.03 and 100.00 from respective standard weeks.

The maximum killing per cent was recorded, 50.38 at grub stage and 100.00 at pupal stage from 15th SW. Ribeiro *et al.* (2010) were recorded that a stinkbug predator (Asopinae) was registered preying on caterpillars of *Brassolis sophorae* L., *Opsiphanes invirae* Hubner (Lepidoptera: Nymphalidae) and *Sibine* spp. (Lepidoptera: Limacodidae), reducing their populations in commercial oil palm plantations in the State of Para, Brazil. Magistrali (2014) record that the occurrence of predatory stinkbugs, *Podisus nigrispinus*, *Brontocoris tabidus* and *Alcaeorrhynchus grandis* in outbreaks of *Nystalea nyseus* in eucalyptus plantations.

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